

The relationship between resiliency, Internal Cohesion and Positive Psychological states in Male and Female Students of Mashhad Farhangian University: A Path Analysis Model

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Abstract

The aim of the present study was to predict resilience, internal cohesion, and individual adjustment according to the components of positive psychology in male and female students of Farhangian University of Mashhad in 2009-2010 and to determine the relationship between these variables. In this study, 314 students (182 males and 132 females) were selected by cluster random sampling method and the questionnaires of positive psychological states (Rajaei, Khoynejad, Nisaei, 2012), adaptation (Bell, 1961), resilience (Connor and Davidson, 2003) and the Internal Cohesion Questionnaire (Kimiaei, Arqbaei, Jozi, 2013) were administered to them. The data of this research were statistically analyzed by path analysis method using AMOS software. The results showed that the path of explaining cohesion based on resilience has become significant with the mediating role of the components of trust in God and gratitude. It can be said that these findings indicate the need to pay attention to positive psychological states in explaining the behavioral, cognitive and emotional levels of students.

Keywords: Positive psychological states, adaptability, resilience, internal cohesion

Introduction:

Given that Iranian society is a young society in terms of age pyramid and most of its population is young people and adolescents, attention to this segment of the population can be necessary and of great importance. According to the World Health Organization, 70% of deaths are behaviors that have their roots in adolescence and can be corrected. The statistics of adolescents with AIDS are also worth considering. During adolescence, there is a tendency for high-risk behaviors such as smoking, drug and alcohol use, unhealthy sex, and other delinquent behaviors that are detrimental to their physical and mental health (Yamamoto and et al, 2008). collage students experience many changes in social and human relationships, such as forming new social networks (Roberts, 2016). The World Health Organization (WHO) classifies

communication skills into basic and advanced groups, with interpersonal communication skills in the basic skills group that students must learn (Joyce and et al, 2018).

At present, existing theories and disciplines about resilience are used in the fields of psychology and ecology. Today, the concept of resilience applies to current distress planning and management (Martin breen and Andries, 2011). Initially, resilience was considered a personality trait that modulates and adapts to the adverse effects of stress (Glickens, 2006; Luthar and et al, 2000). Studies have also shown that relationships based on love and trust provide positive role models and encouragement and reassurance that help ensure resilience in individuals (Wicks, 2009). In terms of resilience outcomes, some studies have suggested the effect of mental health or reduction of emotional problems on life satisfaction, which can be defined by combining things like happiness and success (Yu and et al, 2007; Masten and Wright, 2010). Also, the simultaneous regression of resilience on the factors of spiritual excellence showed that the factor of spiritual connection and spiritual unity were significant predictors of resilience. The results showed the role of spirituality in increasing the resilience capacity of individuals (Hashemi and et al, 2011). Resilience, despite traumatic and threatening conditions, enables a person to acquire the skills to overcome problems, life challenges, and stressful situations (Clauss-Ehlers, 2008). Early theorists of resilience, emphasized the characteristics associated with positive outcomes in the face of life's adversities (Levy and Wall, 2000).

This issue can be related to a person's ability to be cohesive and react healthily to sources of stress. A sense of cohesion is the desire of individuals to see their world as perceptible, manageable, and meaningful (Kravets and et al, 1993). people with information identities have high resistance to stress (Mohsen tabar and et al, 2017). According to the theory, a sense of cohesion is an inner experience that gradually develops during adolescence to reach a relatively stable quality in a person and thus see their world as understandable, manageable, and meaningful (Langeland and Wall, 2008). Antonovsky defines a sense of cohesion as a personal orientation to life and believes that this content can explain why a person can overcome high-stress levels and stay healthy (Bangstone and Lars, 2008). A sense of cohesion is a protective factor against mood swings in severe illnesses and is associated with a reduced risk of mental illness (Kouvonen and et al, 2008).

The positive effects of these structures on physical and mental health have been confirmed in various studies. Seligman categorizes positive emotions into three categories: those related to the past, present, and future. The satisfaction that accompanies the states of fascination or fascination is obtained by engaging in activities involving affirmative powers (Kar, 2006). If people do not have a clear and confident feeling about who they are, they cannot interact with others in a sincere way (Shafiabadi and Naseri, 2016). Positive emotions expand our attention and make us aware of the wider physical and social environment. This expanded attention prepares us to accept new ideas and actions, and more than that. Usually, we become more creative (Seligman, 2010).

Components of Positive Behavior (Positive Psychological Modes): An example of human abilities that make up the main subject of Positive Psychology: Happiness, Pleasure, Flexibility,

Hardiness, Control Personality, Optimism, Optimistic Explanatory Style, Hope, Feeling Effective, Goal Setting, Meaning, Love of Knowledge, Wisdom, Originality, Ability for Psychology, Autonomy, Generosity, Compassion, Empathy, Altruism, Humor, Spirituality (Cohn and Fredrickson, 2010). Also, considering that the concept of cohesion is a personal orientation to life (Hashemi and et al, 2011) and a kind of general orientation that internal and external stimuli that are in the path of life Consider it predictable and explicable (Hakimi and et al, 2017; Sadeghi niri and et al, 2013; Farnam and Madadizade, 2017). Research has shown that teaching positivity in increasing positive psychological states: trust in God, optimism, self-efficacy, conscientiousness, sense of control, purposefulness, hope, life satisfaction, meaningful life, positive mood and happiness, sociability, self-esteem, and sense of worth The feeling of calm, gratitude and forgiveness was influential in the experimental group. Hakimi, astrologer, Rahimian and Kern, Various methods to improve students' academic performance of different levels by Thinkers and experts in the field of psychology have been compiled and employed, including (Nitsch and et al, 2015). overcoming Psychosocial adversity has an essential effect on health-related behaviors, lifestyle modifications, and ultimately reducing the incidence of physical and psychological illnesses (Kahrazehi and et al, 2017; Rahimian and et al, 2013) Abilities such as courage, optimism, interpersonal communication skills, ethics, and hope are shocking psychological injuries (Baileya and et al, 2007; Jabari and et al, 2014). This finding also shows the importance of attention and the development of these positive states. Therefore, psychological interventions have a significant impact on the promotion of students' self-esteem in Iran. Is the degree of resilience predictable based on internal coherence with the mediating role of positive psychology?

Methods

The present study is path analyzing. The study's statistical population was male and female students of Farhangian University: Shahid Beheshti (Male), and Shahid Hasheminejad (Female) in Mashhad, whose number was 3200. To determine the sample size, according to the number of subscales in the study, which is 15 subscales, the sample size of 314 people was selected. Cluster sampling was used to select the sample. Several faculties were randomly selected from the existing faculties, and many classes were randomly selected from each faculty, and questionnaires were distributed among all students in the class.

Resilience Scale: The Conner & Davidson Resistance Scale (CD-RISC1) has 25 items. In this questionnaire, the maximum score is 100, with zero as a minimum score. Also, the score of each subject is equal to the sum of the scores of each of the questions. Connor and Davidson reported 87% of the test-retest reliability of this questionnaire on 24 patients. Convergent validity of this questionnaire was performed on 30 psychiatric patients using the Kobasa hardiness questionnaire. The results showed that the resilience questionnaire was 83% related to the Kobasa hardiness questionnaire, but 76% was related to perceived stress. High levels of resilience are associated with low experienced stress (Conner and Davidson, 2003). In general, the results show the optimal reliability and validity of the resilience questionnaire. The resilience questionnaire in Iran has been standardized by Samani, Jokar and Sahragard, and the results showed that this questionnaire has 0.87 Cronbach's alpha (Samani and et sl, 2007).

Positive Psychology Components Scale: Positive Psychology Models Questionnaire (PPS) has been prepared by Rajaei, Khoynejad, Nesai (2012), which includes 96 questions and a total of 15 positive psychological modes as follows: Sanjay: Trust in God, Optimism, Feeling of efficiency, Conscientiousness Feeling of control, Purposefulness, Hopefulness, Meaningfulness of life, Satisfaction with life, Positive mood and happiness, Being social, Feeling calm, Gratitude Forgiveness. The scoring of this questionnaire is based on the Likert scale from 1 to 5 (from strongly disagree score 1 to agree score 5 strongly). Reliability of this questionnaire has confirmed by Experts. For computing validity, Cronbach's alpha method was used and results shows that there is high validity for this scale (0.837) (Rajaei, Khoynejad, Nesai, 2012).

Internal Cohesion Scale:

Internal Cohesion Questionnaire is a 50-item questionnaire developed by Kimiaei, Arghabaei and jozi. This questionnaire has three subscales to measure the comprehensibility, manageability, and significance of events from the individual's point of view. The significance scale includes 23 questions, and the manageability scale has six questions. The comprehensibility scale has 20 questions and is graded in a 5-point range from very low (1) to very high (5) by the Likert method. Questions 8, 9, 16, 21, 22, 27, 39, 41, 46, 47, 48 are graded inversely so that in the 5-point range, very high (1) to very low (5) scores come. Higher scores indicate great internal cohesion, and lower scores indicate lower internal cohesion. In standardizing this questionnaire, out of 410 subjects sampled in a multi-stage cluster method, 404 questionnaires were obtained, ranging in age from 18 to 40 years and averaging 22.5 years. The Internal Cohesion Questionnaire has a good consistency. Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the whole scale is 0.93 and 927% for the significance subscale and 650% for the manageability subscale 650%, for the comprehensibility subscale 886%. Concurrent validity of the Internal Cohesion Questionnaire was obtained through a significant correlation of 556% with the GHQ1 questionnaire. Also, all subscales have a significant correlation with other general health scales ((Arghabaei and et al, 2013).

Results

The results of descriptive studies of demographic variables of the research are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. demographic variables of research sample members

Variable	Average	Deviation
Age	21/71	2/51
Marital status	Frequency	Frequency percentage
Married	20	6%
Single	294	94%
Degree of	Frequency	Frequency percentage
Persian Literature	59	19%

English	51	16%
Physical education	53	17%
Biochemistry	54	18%
Advice and guidance	53	17%
Mathematics and Physics	44	13%

According to Table 1, it can be seen that the average age of participants in the study was about 21 years. It can also be seen that more sample members were single, and students of Persian literature had a larger share.

Table 2. descriptive report of variables

Variables	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Variables	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Resilience	70.63	15.73	29	117	Meaning of life	11.03	3.74	5	51
Internal cohesion	39.56	8.04	54	219	Life Satisfaction	19.34	3.3	10	28
Trust in God	14.47	3.74	6	25	Positive mood	16.4	4.67	8	5
Upbeat	28.41	5.02	16	39	Social being	9.89	2.83	4	17
Feeling of efficiency	37.77	5.92	24	52	Self-esteem	19.8	4.9	11	66
Conscientiousness	11.93	4.03	5	25	Feeling relaxed	17.05	3.52	9	26
Feeling of control	16.9	3.39	7	24	Appreciation	16.2	4.28	8	46
Targeted	11.16	2.19	4	16	Forgiveness	19.63	3.85	9	28
Hope	10.41	2.4	6	18					

The data in Table 2 show the descriptive indicators of the mean and standard deviation of the subjects in the variables of resilience, positive psychological components, and internal cohesion. To investigate the researcher's hypothesis, path analysis was used in which the paths of research variables are examined relative to each other. Before performing path analysis, the correlation between internal cohesion and resilience with the components of positive psychological states was examined as a mediating variable. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Correlation of positive psychological components with cohesion and resilience

Variables	Resilience	Coherence	Variables	Resilience	Coherence
Trust in God	0.539 **	340/0 **	Life Satisfaction	0.286**	0.061
Upbeat	0.177 *	0.302 **	Positive mood	0.403 **	0.269 **
Feeling of efficiency	0.451 **	0.136 *	Social being	0.591 **	0.532 **
Conscientiousness	0.625 **	0.462 **	Self-esteem	0.227 *	0.010
Feeling of control	0.204 *	0.023	Feeling relaxed	0.014	0.401 **
Targeted	0.184 *	0.107	Appreciation	0.510 **	0.269 **
Hope	0.532 **	0.448 **	Forgiveness	0.246 *	0.231 *
Meaning of life	0.211	0.503			

According to Table 3, it can be seen that the components of the feeling of control, the meaning of life, life satisfaction, self-esteem, and feeling of peace, because they are not significantly related to the other four variables, are removed from the analysis process. The following are the results of path analysis studies.

Table 4. The goodness of the structural model fit

P	CFI	AGFI	GFI	RMSEA	X ² /Df	X ²	F
0.001	0.992	0.951	0.904	0.044	1.68	62.65	39

As shown in Table 4, the ratio of chi-square to the degree of freedom is less than 2.5 and the RMSEA is close to zero. Also, the values of GFI, AGFI, and CFI are close to one. As a result, the proposed model had a probability value of 0.001.

Table 5. Direct, indirect and total effects to predict quality of life

Variable	Direct	Indirect	Total	Probability	Variable	Direct	Indirect	Total	Probability
Trust in God Resilience	0.004	0.016	0.219	0.827	Cohesion * Trust in God	0.087	0.011	7.701	0.0000
Optimism * Resilience	0.115	0.035	3.32	0.000	Cohesion * Optimism	0.550	0.024	2.246	0.000
Feeling of efficiency * Resilience	0.06	0.04	1.504	0.132	Cohesion * Feeling efficient	0.148	0.028	5.278	0.025

Conscientiousness * Resilience	0.042	0.016	2.68	0.007	Coherence * Conscientiousness	0.097	0.011	8.819	0.000
Hope * Resilience	0.043	0.011	3.919	0.000	Cohesion * Hope	0.049	0.088	6.381	0.000
Positive mood * Resilience	0.026	0.021	1.236	0.216	Cohesion * Positive mood	0.072	0.015	4.876	0.000
Sociality * Resilience	0.057	0.010	0.473	0.000	Cohesion * Being social	0.052	0.007	7.174	0.000
Appreciation * Resilience	0.003	0.018	0.192	0.848	Cohesion * Appreciation	0.092	0.013	7.327	0.000
Forgiveness * Resilience	0.102	0.017	6.004	0.000	Cohesion * Forgiveness	0.083	0.012	6.948	0.000

Table 4 shows the extent of each structure's direct, indirect, and total effects on internal cohesion and resilience. It has been found that the path of explaining the inner coherence of the components of trust in God and appreciation based on resilience has become meaningful. It has also been found that the path of explaining the components of appreciation and forgiveness based on resilience has become meaningful.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the predictability of resilience based on internal cohesion with the mediating role of positive psychological components in male and female students of the Farhangian University of Mashhad. Statistical findings show that the regression equation is significant for resilience predictability based on internal cohesion with positive psychological components. Explaining this finding, we can say that positive emotions expand our attention and make us aware of the wider physical and social environment. This expanded attention allows us to accept new ideas and actions. In this way, positive emotions provide us with opportunities to build better relationships and be more productive (Hakimi and et al, 2017). On the other hand, the feeling of failure makes people less resilient and resistant to stress. Therefore, it hurts resilience (Mohsen tabar and et al, 2017). Other studies was in line with our findings such as Aspinwall and et al (2005), Kotera and et al (2021), Lethale and et al (2013) and Uruk and et al (2007) that all of these researches indicated positive relation and effective impact of internal cohesion and positive psychology factors on resilience.

People who evaluate themselves positively have a lot of respect for others (Kar, 2006) and because they can attract the love of others, they have more mental health (Seligman, 2010). Therefore, it can be said that cultivating more positive cognitions such as belief in God, optimism, jokes, enjoyment and enjoyment of friendly social relationships can affect a person's physical and mental health. They also considered that the concept of cohesion is a personal

orientation to life (Hashemi and et al, 2013) and a kind of general orientation that considers the internal and external stimuli in the path of life to be predictable and explicable. In other words, in any functional area, the beliefs of efficiency or judgment that individuals have about their abilities determine the expectations about the outcome and consequences of behaviors. On the other hand, based on the basics of positive psychology, people's sense of control over the resources they have in their relationships with others and when facing tensions, while having more awareness and attention to the existing reality, automatic thoughts and Habitally abandoned and have a more flexible functioning, especially in social relationships and the resulting tensions. Also, according to the theoretical foundations of positive psychology, the advantage of having a sense of control is that it helps people to have a positive return on their behavior. People can only fall in love with themselves if they already have a strong sense of identity. If people do not feel clear and confident about their personality, they can not interact sincerely with others (Shafeiabadi and Naseri, 2016) On the other hand, what causes people to react resiliently to environmental stresses and pressures. There are some personality traits and psychological abilities that allow people to react effectively to problems. In other words, because human beings are different in terms of inner strength, flexibility and tolerance for problems (Galloway and et al, 2005) and also a number of studies have pointed to the effect of mental health or reducing emotional problems on life satisfaction (Kim, Kim and Ko, 2017) It can be said with certainty that the existence of positive adaptation or positive transformation can affect the in / out psychological functioning of individuals through the use of components such as happiness and success, while it may affect some aspects of personal competence and self-efficacy. See lost, but in other aspects of their personality, increase personal self-sufficiency and help to improve the situation (Shshani and Steinmetz, 2014). In terms of resilience outcomes, some studies have suggested the effect of mental health or reduction of emotional problems on life satisfaction, which can be defined by combining things like happiness and success (Yu znd Zhang, 2007; Masten and Wright, 2010). The main goal of positive psychology is to understand and facilitate happiness and mental health. If we divide the positive emotions related to the present into two distinct categories, they include immediate pleasures and more lasting satisfaction that result from positive sensory experiences. Satisfaction that accompanies the states of fascination or fascination is obtained by engaging in activities that involve the use of affirmative powers (Ebrahimi and et al, 2020). But as mentioned, the components of positive psychology underlie the ability of individuals to have more desirable social relationships. To this end, the capabilities of individuals in the areas of personality and psychology, such as resilience and internal cohesion should be improved as a result. The sum of these factors can guarantee more favorable conditions for establishing and benefiting from a social network. One of the limitations of the study was the time of implementation of some questionnaires and lack of control over marital status. Also, the lack of control over the research sample in terms of educational status and personality structures can be one of the limitations of the research. It is suggested that future researchers examine variables related to personality structures and cognitive systems such as thinking in the model studied in the present study.

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